

ISic1493

I.Sicily inscription 1493

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Falcone

Provenance

contrada Scotolo, prop. F. Parlavecchio, Falcone, prov. of Messina

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory 2909

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Εὐσκίς ἔζη
2. σεν ἔτη κη · Ἄσ
3. τομάχις
4. ἔζησεν
5. ἔτη · ιβ ·

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001 with Photograph

Translation (en)

Euskis lived for 28 years. Astomaxis lived for 12 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493877

EDCS 38200028

PHI 313675

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 43
Ferrua, A 1941. *Analecta sicula. Epigraphica*. 3: 252-270. At 253 no.2

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